

Catalogues-as-data: practice, principles, and prospects

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Catalogues are data (Gooding, Terras, Ames eds., 2025; Padilla et al, 2019). And as a precursor to a range of tasks – from using catalogues proxies for understanding the collections they describe to undertaking reparative cataloguing – it is important to get to know that data. Some of the ways to do that are grounded in familiar methodologies. In the case of printed catalogues, for example, page layout can confer information about the priorities of contemporaneous cataloguers, indices about the assumed usages, backgrounds, and knowledges of user communities, marginalia about the liveness, utility, and longevity of a catalogue after publication. In the case of all catalogues – whether card indices, printed volumes, bespoke databases, or federated knowledge bases – the content of the catalogue data can also infer forms of meaning and decision making that may not be elucidated in corresponding institutional archives: descriptive extent can suggest information about the labour available to document collections at specific times; the use of controlled vocabularies can reveal the penetration of local, regional, and international standards; inconsistencies can indicate temporal variations in staffing and information control; evaluative or conditional statements can provide ways into cultures of cataloguing in which cataloguers were operating.

Scholars and practitioners in a range of fields are adopting such approaches to take catalogues as a vital site of enquiry, using catalogues to probe institutional histories, understand the development of collections, and probe barriers to access via modern information infrastructures. Candace Greene (2016) has demonstrated the ways in which contemporary methods for conceptualising anthropological collections can be traced to temporally and institutionally specific reuses of printed ledgers for organising zoological collections. Lucy Havens (2025) has explored how foregrounding the variability of gender biases within archival catalogue data can challenge techno-solutionist approaches to 'debiasing'. Hannah Turner (2020) has made important contributions to our conceptualisation of cataloguing as cultural, including how forms of cataloguing labour and their perceived museological value intersect with gender and technology. Alexandra Ortolja-Baird and Julianne Nyhan (2021) have foregrounded the political in the catalogue, how emphases and omissions enable us to embrace overlapping vocalities and knowledge systems. And Tonya Sutherland and Alyssa Purcell (2021) have articulated how violence and trauma can be caused by uncritical transfers of item records between formats and across time.

In response to this body of work, this panel draws together contributions from practitioners, researchers, and creators of catalogues-as-data. Panellists will report on novel work that stewards, develops, and advances catalogues-as-data in a range of digital humanities contexts. What will emerge are practices, principles, and prospects for future catalogues-as-data work that are grounded in DH Benelux's unique interdisciplinary Digital Humanities community.

Coen Wilders (Head of Collection Information and Archive, Rijksmuseum) will reflect on catalogues as the backbone of knowledge about the Rijksmuseum's collections. These are sources that structure how the museum understands and manages information and data about collections – ranging from object metadata and library and archival records to documentation files, images, and research datasets – created and maintained over generations by curators, conservators, librarians, archivists, and information specialists. Wilders' contribution explores

how the Rijksmuseum is integrating these diverse sources into more coherent collections-as-data services that support deeper inquiry into the museum objects and their historical contexts. Specifically, he will frame this work in relation to selected principles from the 'Santa Barbara Statement on Collections as Data' (Padilla et al, 2019), to consider where institutional practices align with its values and where limitations arise. These include balancing openness with ethical and legal obligations, and reflecting on the principle that collections-as-data designed for everyone serve no one. Ultimately, Wilders will offer a practitioner's perspective on catalogues-as-data across library, archive, and museum domains.

Rebecca Kahn (Postdoctoral Researcher, University of Vienna) has spent several years working with museum collections which are represented as Linked Open Data, and aggregated into large-scale repositories. Her work focuses on the management and handling of what might be considered as troublesome, unruly and sensitive museum objects and their data and the technical and ethical implications embedded in their digital manifestations. Her contribution will expand the discussion about the politics of the catalogue by exploring a case study of how digitised records and images of human remains are presented in different collections. The management and displays of these types of materials in their analogue forms are subject to best practice guidelines and, in some cases, legal constraints. But in the digital world, these guardrails are largely absent. In many cases, objects that would never be on display in a gallery have been made available online, and have spread, via the datastream and facilitated by open licensing regimes, across the web. The discussion will consider the ethical impact of this "digital seepage" as well as the technical considerations required to mitigate it, and open up a broader discussion about how to balance these practical realities in the catalogues-as-data approach.

Steven Claeysens (Curator of Digital Collections, National Library of the Netherlands) reflects on three notions as they appear in library catalogues: the published, the preserved, and the digitised. *The published* refers to the totality of books that have been published. *The preserved* encompasses those for which at least one copy has survived in a public institution. *The digitised* represents the subset made publicly available in digital form. In the Netherlands, roughly speaking, the first category is represented in the national bibliography, the second in the national catalogue, and the third in the KB catalogue. His contribution will argue that catalogues-as-data are crucial for understanding the national corpora of digitised materials. They not only serve as the indispensable starting point for digitisation selection, they also underpin the examination, evaluation, and contextualisation of large collections of digitised materials, a fundamental condition for assessing potential use, identifying biases, and understanding both the limitations and the opportunities of a collection.

James Baker (Professor of Digital Humanities, Southampton) will present early-stage research that uses computational methods – pairwise matching and community detection – to characterise patterns and clusters in catalogue data based on features of catalogue data that represent forms of knowledge labour (as opposed to features that represent the collections that catalogue data describes). Using the 23,491 catalogue records in National Library of Scotland's Moving Image Archive as a test case, his contribution will present this work as a precursor to estimating when, by whom (at an abstract 'group' level rather than person specific level), and through which mental models and standards that communities of cataloguing emerge. In contrast to Baker's previous work with catalogue data, which examined the features of a corpus of catalogue data created by a single cataloguer and used that to estimate

transmission over space and time, this research takes a data-led approach to identifying forms of knowledge labour. It argues that characterising patterns and clusters in catalogue data is not only a necessary step in using catalogues-as-data to stand-in for the collections they describe, but also opens up new questions around histories of knowledge production, reparative cataloguing, and model training using catalogue data.

Sven Lieber (Data Manager, Royal Library of Belgium) will discuss the importance of FAIR and persistently findable metadata in catalogues-as-data work. High-quality, well-structured metadata is crucial because it underpins both the computational methods used in Digital Humanities research and the study of metadata itself - an often overlooked but valuable research object (Lahti et al., 2019). Many techniques, such as Named Entity Linking (NEL), depend on rich and interoperable entities, yet researchers still spend much of their time cleaning data instead of analysing it. Bibliographic metadata for example, is rarely ready for quantitative research: harmonization workflows are essential to transform catalog records into reliable research data (Malínek et al., 2024). This makes data curation and data publication a core responsibility of cultural heritage institutions such as national libraries, whose sustained efforts ensure that metadata becomes persistently findable, reusable, and fit for computational analysis. Such practices align with the broader vision of integrated research data infrastructures, where well-curated metadata forms a stable foundation for transparent, collaborative, and innovative digital scholarship.

Catalogues-as-data, then, intersects with a broad range of concerns in the Digital Humanities, from collection histories to data ontologies, computational methods to collection access, data management to knowledge equity. Looking beyond DH, the contributions of the panel are situated within and alongside a wider body of work, anchored around critical data studies, that is seeking to critique practices of care, scale, and forgetting in dataset production, management, and use, drawing on classic texts such as Geoffrey Bowker and Susan Leigh Star's *Sorting Things Out* (2000), a call to narrativise often seemingly commonsense infrastructures of classification, organisation, and explanation. At a time when there are ever fewer barriers to accessing both high-performance computation and machine approaches to computational analysis of catalogue data, we argue that the grounded and critical approaches to catalogues-as-data advanced by this panel are vital.

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